

A Qualitative Study to Assess the Impact of Hostel Life on Undergraduate Medical Students

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Abstract:

Background: The period of transition from adolescence to adulthood is marked by notable changes in an individual's personality and behavior, primarily influenced by genetics, although interactions with their social environment also play a part. Teenagers living in hostels at universities who are not living with their families may therefore be impacted by their surroundings. Therefore the goal of the present study mainly focuses on learning about students' expectations and happiness with their hostel experience and how that affects their academic achievement.

Material and Methods: This qualitative study was conducted in a tertiary level medical college in Punjab. A qualitative survey was conducted by Focus group discussion among undergraduate medical students. A total of 8 male students and 8 female students, are included in this study. Two focus group discussions were conducted. The study participants were asked about their opinions regarding the impact of hostel life on the behaviour and personality of medical students. FGD was conducted employing a focus group discussion guide. The data from the FGD was recorded and the collected data were entered in Microsoft Excel and analysed based on systematic coding. After being coded, the segments that shared a common subject were categorized as constructive and destructive domains.

Results: Students gain experience interacting with a variety of people while living in hostels, and their patience also grows there. It equips students to handle difficulties that arise in real life. The constructive theme was categorized into the following domains: Personality, Collaboration, Academic performance, long-lasting bonding and developing life skills. The destructive theme was categorized as addictive behaviour, emotional imbalance, peer pressure and financial issues. The majority of the male students living in hostels suffer from substance abuse and peer pressure.

Conclusion: Medical students have a favourable educational atmosphere, but they also face a number of problems and a great deal of academic stress, which negatively impacts their academic performance.

Keywords: Hostel Life, Behaviour, Academic Performance.

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Introduction

University student life is a stage between adolescence and adulthood, following which people often assume their adult responsibilities. It's a tumultuous stage of development where students' personalities and behaviour are notably altered. [1] According to research studies, personality development throughout the transition from childhood to adulthood is supported by both hereditary and environmental factors. [2] Hostels are thought of as residential areas owned by schools, colleges, or universities; for students with a warden as head. These students are from diverse ethical, social, geographic, and financial backgrounds. Young students who live in hostels, apart from their families, have a new

experience as they learn how to live independently, become more adapted to living with roommates and other students, share space, utilities, and solutions, etc. [3, 4] Each of these components has the potential to shape a student's personality. In addition, the residents are required to follow certain guidelines, which help them become more disciplined and punctual. Studies have shown that the hostel residents exhibit higher levels of determination, self-sufficiency, confidence, and optimism compared to non-resident students. A survey on the benefits and drawbacks of living in hostels provides perspectives from students. [5-7] The primary benefit of living in a hostel is that it allows students

to learn independence by empowering them to complete all of their work on their own.

They also know the value of finding time to use the gym, play areas, library, and reading room and also critical to allocate time for training to enhance abilities and promote healthy development. [8] Hostel residents face a variety of challenges and obstacles, including financial difficulties, problems adjusting to their new living arrangements, feelings of helplessness and sadness, peer pressure as well as changes in their sleeping and nutrition routines. Studies indicate that students living in hostels are more likely to exhibit empathy, altruistic behaviour, and emotional instability. [9] A survey on the benefits and drawbacks of living in hostels provides perspectives from students. Hence this study was conducted to assess the impact of hostel life among the undergraduate medical students.

Objectives

- To study the psychological and behavioural impact of hostel life.
- To study the problems faced by undergraduate medical students in learning environment.
- To suggest recommendations for improving quality of hostel life

Material and Methods

It was a Qualitative study conducted in medical campus of a medical college in Punjab over a period of 6 months in undergraduate medical MBBS students who were willing to give consent.

After getting informed written consent from the study participant's qualitative survey was done by Focus group discussion among the medical students.

Focus group discussion (FDG):

After getting permission from the Dean, two FGD's were conducted among the medical students. A total of 16 students, 8 male and 8 female, two from each professional year of MBBS were included in the study. Participants selected by convenient purposive sampling.

The participants were invited personally for focus group discussion on the study topic. The members of the group had the lively and active conversation. Trained moderator who was well verse in "English" and assisted by the note taker carried out the focus group discussion after taking written informed consent.

The purpose of the study was explained to each participant, and permission was obtained to record the conversation.

Discussions focused on learning about students' expectations and happiness with their hostel experience and how that affects their academic achievement. The approximate time duration of FGD was around 90 minutes. After completion of FGD, the findings were shared and feedback was obtained as a form of "member checking" to enhance the validity of the findings.

Chart 1:

Data analysis

At the end of each focus group session, participant's responses were summarized to help assure saturation. Data obtained was transcribed and a free listing of responses was done to identify themes, domains, and sub domains.

Ethical issues

Beri *et al.*

Participants were informed about the study and informed consent was obtained. This study was presented to Institutional Ethical Committee of Adesh University.

Results

The qualitative research was conducted among MBBS students to explore the psychological and

behavioural impact of hostel life. The Focus Group discussion was conducted among eight female and eight male MBBS hostel students separately.

The two students were selected from each professional course from first-year MBBS to final-year MBBS for a sample size of eight. The focus group discussion started with basic questions about their

demographic information. The students were enquired about how they felt about their hostel. Then, slowly their questions regarding to impact of hostel life based on constructive and destructive factors were discussed.

The questionnaire which was utilised in the interview was listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Questionnaire used by FGD guide

1	How do you think hostel affects the personality of the student?
2	How does hosteller manage his time effectively?
3	What is the role of physical fitness in student's life?
4	What is the impact of ragging in hostel life?
5	What do you think about freedom in hostel?
6	What are the incidences of drug abuse in hostel?
7	Does living away from family affect behaviour of hostellers?
8	Does hosteller's relationship with parents weaken due to less interaction with them?
9	How do hostellers feel being independent?
10	How does junior-senior relationship help hosteller?
11	Are there more chances of stress disorders in hosteller due to competition among peers?
12	What are your views on punctuality in hosteller?
13	What are emotional changes one experience in hostels?
14	How does an introvert adjust in hostel and with his/her roommates?
15	How do you manage your studies in the presence of your roommate?
16	Do group studies in hostel improve learning and scoring? What are your views on this?
17	How do you cope up with your studies during Dj nights and birthday parties?
18	What role does student/hostile environment provide during exams?
19	How does learning in hostel develop competition and self- assessment?
20	What is the impact of your seniors on your hostel learning and studies?
21	How does absence of parent's sight affect learning in hostel?
22	Do you feel sleepy after taking meals? What do you do in hostels to save your study time and get back to study?

The students informed that staying hostel reduced their distance to education and also it provided shelter and basic needs. The themes which students discussed were illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Impact of Hostel Life

The constructive theme was categorized into the following domains: Personality, Collaboration, Academic performance, long-lasting bonding and developing life skills. The destructive theme was categorized as addictive behaviour, emotional imbalance, peer pressure and financial issues. The following codes were used, physical fitness, self-grooming, maturity, boost confidence, boost communication skills, loss of stage fear and become extrovert in the personality category.

The students informed that they were involved in outdoor games and indoor games when they enquired about how they manage their time effectively. The students were asked about their physical fitness and one of the male students answered that

“I maintained my physical fitness by going to gym”. “Boost the confidence of the student”

Due to the availability of gyms, students were utilizing that for their physical fitness which increases that personality. Medical students are not only involved in academics, but they should also maintain their physical fitness.

The student informed that living away from life changes her life to some extent among hostellers. The first thing should be a hosteller that they should adjust to that environment and their roommates. The students in their homes have the support of parents, but in hostels, they should deal with their problems with their roommates. They are supposed to make everything on their own and they mould themselves to be mature people to handle things effectively. At home, they have less opportunity to deal with problems and in a hostel, they become confident and extrovert. They are learning to self-groom themselves and being mature.

The other student stated “Living in hostel has increased my level of maturity with time”.

One female student reported, “First I wasn’t very open to share anything with anyone but now after staying in hostel and having a roommate I am able to share my feeling with him without being judged”.

Hostel life gives them a variety of exposures. They have an opportunity to learn many things about the external world of reality and to interact with different kinds of people. Medical students are mixed with many groups of people and they come to know different cultures and make them confident to interact with them and they boost their communication skills.

The other student said “We learnt to interact with students from different places and different cultures”.

The medical colleges not only conduct academic festivals but also conduct extracurricular activities and other programs. In the hostel, they have enough

time to discuss with their peers and to be involved in group activities. They are involving themselves in planning, conducting, and making financial for being a part of other programs. They were involved in that program, which they communicated with all peers and boost their confidence.

The student from the hostel also stated “I have boosted my communication skills by joining different clubs and taking part in extracurricular activities”.

The student stated, “I have gained the quality of team spirit as I passed from one professional to another”.

One of the answers where “College has provided me the confidence to be on the stage”.

In the hostel, students learn to move into a society of their own, which gives them an attempt to learn about society and acquire social skills such as communication, relating with others, management, and leadership qualities. The Indian Medical graduate should be a leader, and a good communicator, in the hostel premises they learned these things by being hostellers. They boost their communication skills and the stage fear would be gone. The group involvement makes them to learn team spirit and group dynamics to allow the positive flows in group activity. They also learned to avoid conflicts during group activities.

The main reason for staying in a hostel is to make them good academicians. They prefer hostel to spend adequate time and to focus on their studies. This led to improving the educational performance of the hostel students.

One student stated that “I manage my time which keeps me focused and increase my efficiency to do work”.

The seniors of medical colleges will also give their experience with their positive as well as negative views. In many situations, they help their juniors handle the situation and share their own experience too. And thus, the medical student would engage in that environment and cope up with the stress. One female student stated, “My seniors always share their experience and provide us help in every situation which has helped us to be more patient and cope up with stress”

The student once they have vacated the hostel, would have many positive thoughts, confidence, communication skills, and pleasant feelings. Once they meet again, they would have a good memory and cherish their emotional bonds.

One male student said, (sharing his personal experience) “Whenever I get call from old friends it has always felt great because that emotional bond always persists and cherishing those old memories and reliving them make me feel more lively”.

So, being a hosteller increases their self-grooming, maturity, confidence communication skills. They have lost their fear of facing social issues and they becoming extroverts. They have the capability to work in the team and also to cope with the stress. Academic performance also increases and group studies make them to better understand the curriculum.

The hostel environment also provides some negative experiences. Drug and alcohol consumption was increasing among students due to their peer pressure. In the hostel environment, there were no parental restrictions and students believed themselves as independent and no one restricted them. They believed that they could do anything and fear for nothing. Medical students could know the effects of alcohol consumption and drug addiction; however, they are involved in these vulnerable activities.

The male student stated that “Alcohol, cannabinoids, opioid, hash and weed are prevalent in hostel and are common. There spread is like a chain reaction in the hostel”.

The student stated that “I feel students do it for fun, enjoyment and for trying something New; As they get freedom from parents and some believe that it gives them feeling of maturity

The students staying in the hostel come from different places and cultures. The different attitudes of students and their peer pressure have some impact on their peers. They have to spend many on things and eatables. The student stated that “I got some back stabbing from friends at certain points in Hostel life”.

The student stated that “I was not able to mix up with my peers that decreased my self-control and made me feel lonely and isolated”.

The student stated that “Poor Academic performance brings insecurity among students”.

The student stated that “I believe if the senior is a good person u will get positive guidance but a bad senior will end up giving you negative advices that will hinder you academically, physically as well as psychologically

The student stated that “After coming to hostel i have started spending haphazardly onclothes”.

The student stated that “I frequently eat outside which has increased my monthly expenses”.

Discussion

A qualitative research was conducted to understand the impact of hostel on behavior and personality in the life of hostel students. During the discussion the students residing in hostel openly spoke about the various benefits of staying in the hostel such as

ease to access the medical Institute and provision of shelter away from home. It saves time and provides opportunity to continue the process of education.

Hostel serves as a sanctuary for students where families are broken. In such scenarios hostelgive them a safe haven along with peace of mind and focus to concentrate in the studies.

Students also pointed out the various constructive impacts of hostellers like becoming independent, gaining knowledge, mastering skills and comprehensive development.

There were some participants who highlighted the destructive impacts of hostel life.

Students are send to hostel at an early age by their parents which results in homesickness, inability to adjust in hostile environment, health problems and indulgence in drug addiction to cope up with the stress.

Our study is similar to a study conducted by Asir Ajmal et al [10] stated that hostel students are commonly connected with characteristics such as confidence, punctuality, social skills, reality, compromise, responsibility, and sharpness in many domains of life. He also stated that male students are negatively affected because of peer pressure and drug use.

Another study conducted by Wahid et al also found that academic performance was positively and significantly correlated with quality of life and academic stress which is comparable to our study report. [11]

The present study showed no significant effect of family structure on students’ academic performance which is similar to a study conducted by Azumah FD et al. [12]

Conclusion

The present study was conducted to assess the impact of living in a hostel on medical students. It emphasized the experiences, modifications in behaviour, and traits of personality of the hostel students. It also examines the gender disparities between the housemates. The findings indicate that male students living in dorms are more likely to experience negative effects from their stay because of peer pressure and drug usage.

Limitations

- Small size and single –centered study.
- The larger sample size might be considered for generalizing results.

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